

Cyanogen Compounds of Pentavalent Rhenium

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In a previous communication¹, the acid-association constants of dioxotetracyano-rhenate(v) have been reported. Job's method of continued variations indicates that the violet colour formed by addition of acid to a solution of $K_2 [ReO_4 (CN)_4]$, is due to the species $[ReO(OH)(CN)_3]^{2-}$.

By the action of HCl (dil.) on potassium dioxotetracyanorhenate(v), the free acid, $H [ReO(OH)(H_2O)(CN)_3]$, was obtained¹. This is diamagnetic; but after making the diamagnetic corrections for the ligands, a small paramagnetism ($\mu_{eff}=0.39$ B.M. at 26°) exists for the rhenium ion. Similar observations with other $Re(v)$ complexes have been recently reported². On the basis of conductometric and potentiometric titrations with alkali, it has been shown¹ that the acid primarily behaves as a monobasic one in solution but is present in equilibrium with its tautomeric dibasic form $H_2 [ReO(OH)_2(CN)_3]$. The salts of both the mono and the dibasic forms have been isolated. The sodium and the potassium salts of the monobasic acid have been prepared by addition of one equivalent of the corresponding alkali hydroxide or an excess of the corresponding alkali acetate to a solution of the free acid and precipitating with ethanol. The salts of the dibasic acid have been obtained in a similar manner by addition of an excess of alkali hydroxide to the acid solution. The sodium and the potassium salts, when dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 (conc.), became anhydrous. The analytical data are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Found.			Compound.	Requires.		
%Re.	%N.	%Na or K.		%Re.	%N.	%Na or K.
56.2	12.0	6.5	$Na [ReO(OH)(H_2O)(CN)_3]$	55.1	12.4	6.8
53.2	11.6	11.4	$K [ReO(OH)(H_2O)(CN)_3]$	52.6	11.9	11.0
52.1	12.1	12.5	$Na_2 [ReO(OH)_2(CN)_3]$	51.7	11.7	12.8
47.3	10.6	20.6	$K_2 [ReO(OH)_2(CN)_3]$	47.5	10.7	20.0

The salts of the monobasic acid are brown-black and those of the dibasic acid, brown-violet in colour. Their aqueous solutions are deep brown and form brown precipitates with heavy metal salts. The molecular conductances of potassium salts of the mono and the dibasic forms at a dilution of 1024 litres are 128 and 303 mho respectively at 30°, indicating that the salts are uni-univalent and uni-bivalent types, respectively. Details of the work will be published later.

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1. Chakravorti, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 477.

2. Beard *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 707.

